

Note on sums of binomial coefficients $\binom{n}{k}$

Abstract

In this note we discuss formulas for partial or total sums of binomial coefficients $\binom{n}{k}$, keeping n constant and increasing the k values, such as $\binom{7}{2} + \binom{7}{3} + \binom{7}{4} + \dots$, or keeping k constant and increasing the n values, such as $\binom{5}{4} + \binom{6}{4} + \binom{7}{4} + \dots$. The increments of n or k can be integer or fractional numbers and different from each other.

Note on sums of binomial coefficients

An explicit formula for partial sums with constant n is given in the Note "*Partial sum of binomial coefficients*" (zenodo.org/records/3592269). For the formula, see note ¹ below.

For completeness' sake, I would like to remind of the well-known equation $\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} = 2^n$ (see G.E. Andrews - Number Theory. Dover P.0486/68252/8, p. 34, exercise 2). This relationship is derived from Newton's formula $(a + b)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} a^{n-k} b^k$ for $a = b = 1$

Note that this equation can be generalized to the following relations, which are obtained by differentiating Newton's formula respect to a and then setting $a = b = 1$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n k \binom{n}{k} = n * 2^{n-1} \quad (a)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n k^2 \binom{n}{k} = (n + n^2) * 2^{n-2} \quad (b)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n k^3 \binom{n}{k} = (n^3 + 3n^2) * 2^{n-3} \quad (c)$$

An example for the last relation is, for $n = 6$,

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{6}{1} + 2^3 \binom{6}{2} + 3^3 \binom{6}{3} + 4^3 \binom{6}{4} + 5^3 \binom{6}{5} + 6^3 \binom{6}{6} &= 6 + 8 * 15 + 27 * 20 + 64 * 15 + 125 * 6 + 216 \\ &= 2592 \end{aligned}$$

From formula (c) we have $2^3(6^3 + 3 * 6^2) = 8(216 + 108) = 2592$

- The sum of binomials with constant k is less known. However, in G. E. Andrews, p. 34, exercise 5, we have this remarkable formula

$$\sum_{n=n_0}^{n_f} \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n_f + 1}{k + 1} \quad (1)$$

For example, for $k = 3$, $n_0 = 3$, $n_f = 8$, we have:

$$^1 \sum_{k=k_0}^{k=k_f} \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n}{k_0} \times \left\{ 1 + \frac{m}{k_0+1} \left(1 + \frac{m-1}{k_0+2} \left(1 + \frac{m-2}{k_0+3} \dots \left(1 + \frac{n+1-k_f}{k_f} \right) \right) \right) \right\} \text{ where } m = n - k_0$$

$$\binom{3}{3} + \binom{4}{3} + \binom{5}{3} + \binom{6}{3} + \binom{7}{3} + \binom{8}{3} = \binom{9}{4} = 126$$

A justification of this formula is given in Appendix A. As we will see later, this formula is valid only for increments of n equal to 1 and if integer and fractional numbers are not mixed. Contrary to what happens when adding with constant n , in case of constant k , using the (1), sums can also be calculated for $n_0 > k$

For example, let $n_0 = 5, k = 3, n_f = 8$, we have:

$$\binom{5}{3} + \binom{6}{3} + \binom{7}{3} + \binom{8}{3} = 10 + 20 + 35 + 56 = 121$$

The sum for $n_0 = 3$ is $\binom{9}{4} = 126$, from which we must subtract $\binom{3}{3} + \binom{4}{3} = \binom{5}{4} = 5$

Consequently, $\sum_{n=5}^8 \binom{n}{3} = \binom{9}{8} - \binom{5}{4} = 126 - 5 = 121$

Therefore, **for $k < n_0$** we have:

$$\sum_{n=n_0}^{n_f} \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n_f+1}{k+1} - \binom{n_0}{k+1} \quad (2)$$

We already said that **(1), and consequently (2), are not valid if integer and fractional numbers are mixed.**

For example, let $n_0 = 1, n_f = 3$ but $k = 1.5$. We have:

$$\binom{1}{1.5} + \binom{2}{1.5} + \binom{3}{1.5} = \binom{4}{2.5} = 5.432488724$$

While direct calculation gives: $4244132 + 1.69765 + 3.395305 = 5.517371$, which is incorrect.

Note that formula (1), and consequently formula (2), are correct even if both n and k are fractional provided that $n_0 = k$.

For example, for $n_0 = k = \frac{3}{2}$ and $n_f = \frac{9}{2}$, we have: $\binom{1.5}{1.5} + \binom{2.5}{1.5} + \binom{3.5}{1.5} + \binom{4.5}{1.5} = \binom{5.5}{2.5} = 14.4375$

The direct calculation gives $1 + 2.5 + 4.375 + 6.5625 = 14.437$, which is the correct result.

Appendix A provides a justification of (1), clarifying the reason for these behaviors.

- A general formula, valid for n and k integer or fractional numbers, even if mixed together, but with the increment of n equal 1, is given below. It is similar to that seen in the Note already mentioned (zenodo.org/records/3592269).

It arises from the consideration that the first addend of the sum is, by definition, $\frac{n_0!}{k!(n_0-k)!}$, while the second addend is $\frac{(n_0+1)!}{k!(n_0+1-k)!}$; so the ratio of the second addend divided by the first is:

$$\frac{(n_0+1)!}{k!(n_0+1-k)!} \cdot \frac{k!(n_0-k)!}{n_0!} = \frac{n_0+1}{n_0-k+1}$$

Likewise, the ratio between the third and the second addend is $\frac{n_0+2}{n_0-k+2}$

Proceeding similarly with subsequent addends we get:

$$\sum_{n=n_0}^{n_f} \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n_0}{k} + \binom{n_0+1}{k} + \binom{n_0+2}{k} + \dots = \binom{n_0}{k} \left(1 + \frac{n_0+1}{n_0-k+1} \left(1 + \frac{n_0+2}{n_0-k+2} \left(1 + \frac{n_0+3}{n_0-k+3} (1 + \dots) \right) \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

For example, for $k = 3, n_0 = 8, n_f = 11$, namely for

$$\binom{8}{3} + \binom{9}{3} + \binom{10}{3} + \binom{11}{3} = 56 + 84 + 120 + 165 = 425,$$

from (3) we have:

$$\binom{8}{3} \left(1 + \frac{8+1}{8-3+1} \left(1 + \frac{8+2}{8-3+2} \left(1 + \frac{8+3}{8-3+3} \right) \right) \right) = 56 \left(1 + \frac{9}{6} \left(1 + \frac{10}{7} \left(1 + \frac{11}{8} \right) \right) \right) = 56 * 7.58928... = 425$$

With this formula we can recalculate the case with $n_0 = 1, n_f = 3$ and $k = 1.5$ where (1) fails. We have:

$$\binom{1}{1.5} \left[1 + \frac{2}{2-1.5} \left(1 + \frac{3}{3-1.5} \right) \right] = .424413 * \left(1 + \frac{2}{.5} \left(1 + \frac{3}{1.5} \right) \right) = 5.517371$$

which is the correct result.

A more complex example with n_0, n_f, k fractional is the following:

$$n_0 = \frac{8}{3} \quad n_f = \frac{11}{3} \quad k = \frac{1}{5}$$

$$\binom{8/3}{1/5} + \binom{11/3}{1/5} + \binom{14/3}{1/5} = 1.36387 + 1.44256 + 1.50715 = 4.3135$$

From (3) we have:

$$\binom{8/3}{1/5} * \left(1 + \frac{8/3+1}{8/3+1-1/5} \left(1 + \frac{8/3+2}{8/3+2-1/5} \right) \right) = 1.36387 * \left(1 + \frac{3.6666}{3.4666} \left(1 + \frac{4.6666}{4.4666} \right) \right) = 1.36387 * 3.16274 = 4.3135$$

which is the correct result.

However, please note that even in this case the **n increase is 1**.

- Let's consider the case in which the increase in n , which here we indicate by Δ , is fractional as, for example, in the following case:

$$\binom{8/3}{1/5} + \binom{3}{1/5} + \binom{10/3}{1/5} = 1.36387 + 1.3921 + 1.41822 = 4.17419 \quad \text{where we have } \Delta = \frac{1}{3}.$$

If Δ is fractional, formula (3) becomes (see Appendix B for details):

$$\binom{n_0}{k} \left(1 + \frac{(n_0 + \Delta)! * (n_0 - k)!}{n_0! * (n_0 + \Delta - k)!} \left(1 + \frac{(n_0 + 2\Delta)! * (n_0 + \Delta - k)!}{(n_0 + 2\Delta - k)! * (n_0 + \Delta)!} (1 + \dots) \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

For example, we have $n_0 = \frac{8}{3}$ $k = \frac{1}{5}$ $\Delta = \frac{1}{3}$, and therefore:

$$\binom{8/3}{1/5} \left(1 + \frac{(8/3 + 1/3)! * (8/3 - 1/5)!}{(8/3)! * (8/3 + 1/3 - 1/5)!} \left(1 + \frac{(8/3 + 2/3)! * (8/3 + 1/3 - 1/5)!}{(8/3 + 2/3 - 1/5)! * (8/3 + 1/3)!} (1 + \dots) \right) \right) =$$

$$1.36387 * \left(1 + \frac{3! * 2.46666!}{(8/3)! * 2.8!} \left(1 + \frac{(10/3)! * 2.8!}{(10/3 - 1/5)! * 3!} \right) \right) = 4.1741\dots$$

which is the correct result.

- Sometimes it is useful to calculate the sum of binomials where both n and k have constant increments, Δ_n and Δ_k , different from each other, but integers, and $\Delta_n > \Delta_k$. For example, in the sum ($n=7$ and $k=4$)

$\binom{7}{4} + \binom{12}{7} + \binom{17}{10} + \binom{22}{13}$ where the increment of n , Δ_n , is 5 and the increment of k , Δ_k , is 3 we have, by direct calculation:

$$35 + 792 + 19448 + 497420 = 517695$$

Formula (4) becomes, with $m = \Delta_n - \Delta_k = 5 - 3 = 2$,

$$\binom{n}{k} \left[1 + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\dots(n+\Delta_n)}{(k+1)(k+2)\dots(k+\Delta_k)} \right. \\ \left. * \frac{1}{(n-k+1)(n-k+2)\dots(n-k+m)} \left(1 + \frac{(n+\Delta_n+1)(n+\Delta_n+2)\dots(n+\Delta_n+\Delta_n)}{(k+\Delta_k+1)(k+\Delta_k+2)\dots(k+\Delta_k+\Delta_k)} \right) \right. \\ \left. * \frac{1}{(n-k+m+1)(n-k+m+2)\dots(n-k+m+m)} (1 + \dots) \right] \quad (5)$$

However, this complex-looking formula is easy to use, as can be seen in the calculation of the example given above. From (5) we have

$$35 \left(1 + \frac{8 * 9 * 10 * 11 * 12}{5 * 6 * 7} \right. \\ \left. * \frac{1}{4 * 5} \left(1 + \frac{13 * 14 * 15 * 16 * 17}{8 * 9 * 10} * \frac{1}{6 * 7} \left(1 + \frac{18 * 19 * 20 * 21 * 22}{11 * 12 * 13} * \frac{1}{8 * 9} \right) \right) \right) \\ = 517695$$

In the case of $\Delta_n = \Delta_k = \Delta$, formula (5) simplifies and becomes:

$$\binom{n}{k} \left(1 + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\dots(n+\Delta)}{(k+1)(k+2)\dots(k+\Delta)} \left(1 + \frac{(n+\Delta+1)(n+\Delta+2)\dots(n+\Delta+\Delta)}{(k+\Delta+1)(k+\Delta+2)\dots(k+\Delta+\Delta)} (1 + \dots) \right) \right) \quad (5bis)$$

For example, with $\Delta_n = \Delta_k = 3$, we get

$$\binom{7}{4} + \binom{10}{7} + \binom{13}{10} + \binom{16}{13} = 35+120+286+560 = 1001$$

and from (5bis), we have

$$35 \left(1 + \frac{8 * 9 * 10}{5 * 6 * 7} \left(1 + \frac{11 * 12 * 13}{8 * 9 * 10} \left(1 + \frac{14 * 15 * 16}{11 * 12 * 13} \right) \right) \right) = 1001$$

Appendix A

Let's justify formula (1) [here below]

$$\sum_{k=n=n_0}^{n_f=n+m} \binom{n}{k} = \binom{n_f+1}{k+1} \quad (1)$$

Below, for simplicity, we will write n instead of n_0 and $n + m$ instead of n_f

At the left of the equal we have the sum:

$$\frac{1}{0!} + \frac{n+1}{1!} + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!} + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)}{3!} + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots(n+m)}{m!}$$

which becomes:

$$\frac{n+2}{1!}, \text{ when only having the first two terms (addends)}$$

$$\frac{(n+2)(n+3)}{2!}, \text{ when having the first three terms}$$

$$\frac{(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)}{3!}, \text{ when having the first four terms ...}$$

$$\frac{(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)\dots(n+m+1)}{m!}, \text{ when having the first } m \text{ terms.}$$

From (1), on the right side we have:

$$\frac{(n+m+1)!}{(n+1)!(n+m+1-n-1)!} = \frac{(n+m+1)!}{(n+1)! * m!} = \frac{(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)\dots(n+m+1)}{m!}$$

which is the same formula seen on the left.

Of course, simplifications like $\frac{(n+m+1)!}{(n+1)!} = (n+2)(n+3)(n+4)\dots(n+m+1)$, are possible only if we have factorials of numbers (both integers and fractionals), without mixing integer and fractional numbers.

Appendix B

The first addend of the sum is, by definition,

$$\binom{n_0}{k} = \frac{n_0!}{k!(n_0-k)!}$$

while the second is:

$$\binom{n_0+\Delta}{k} = \frac{(n_0+\Delta)!}{k!(n_0+\Delta-k)!}$$

Therefore, the ratio between the two addends is:

$$\frac{2^\circ}{1^\circ} = \frac{(n_0+\Delta)!}{k!(n_0+\Delta-k)!} * \frac{k!(n_0-k)!}{n_0!} = \frac{(n_0+\Delta)!}{n_0!} * \frac{(n_0-k)!}{(n_0+\Delta-k)!}$$

The third addend is:

$$\binom{n_0+2\Delta}{k} = \frac{(n_0+2\Delta)!}{k!(n_0+2\Delta-k)!}$$

Therefore, the ratio $\frac{3^\circ}{2^\circ}$ becomes:

$$\frac{(n_0 + 2\Delta)! * (n_0 + \Delta - k)!}{(n_0 + 2\Delta - k)! * (n_0 + \Delta)!}$$

And so on.